

Molecular phylogenetic analysis of *Echinococcus granulosus sensu lato* infecting sheep in Italy

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ARTICLE INFO

Keywords:

Cystic echinococcosis
Echinococcus granulosus sensu stricto
Sheep
Italy

ABSTRACT

Cystic Echinococcosis (CE), caused by the larval form of *Echinococcus granulosus sensu lato*, is a neglected zoonosis still threatening public health worldwide. In Italy different epidemiological scenarios were reported depending on the geographical area and associated socio-economic activities. Although in northern Italy the occurrence of *E. granulosus* is considered sporadic, in the southern regions and, particularly in Sardinia, CE prevalence reaches high levels. We analysed CE cysts collected from infected sheep from various areas of mainland Italy and the Sardinia island, with the main objective to investigate intergenotypic and intragenotypic variations at national level. CE cysts were collected from slaughtered sheep following post mortem inspection at local abattoirs. Total genomic DNA was extracted and amplification and sequencing of the partial mitochondrial genes *nad5* and *cox1* were performed. A Bayesian phylogenetic tree was estimated on a *nad5* dataset ($n = 260$) composed of *E. granulosus* samples from this study ($n = 126$) and all the *nad5* haplotypes available in GenBank ($n = 134$). In addition, haplotype network, diversity and neutrality analysis were performed on *nad5* and *cox1* sequences of Italian origin obtained in this study. *E. granulosus sensu stricto* (s.s.) was found to be the only *Echinococcus* species infecting sheep in Italy, mainly represented by G1 genotype (76 %) and, to a lower extent, by G3 genotype (24 %). Phylogenetic analyses revealed 40 *nad5* and 33 *cox1* haplotypes, and the presence of two founder haplotypes, belonging to G1 and G3 genotype, showing 100 % similarity with DNA sequences from different geographic regions. The lack of geographical segregation, high haplotype and low nucleotide diversity coupled with significant negative values of Tajima's D and Fu's Fs observed in this study indicated high genetic variation and demographic expansion of *E. granulosus* s.s. in Italy.

1. Introduction

Cystic Echinococcosis (CE) is a zoonotic disease caused by the metacystode stage of *Echinococcus granulosus sensu lato* (s.l.). CE is considered an important public health concern and it has been included by the World Health Organization (WHO) in a list of seven neglected zoonotic diseases requiring priority intervention. *E. granulosus* s.l. is a parasitic flatworm belonging to the class Cestoda whose life cycle includes intermediate (wild and domestic ungulates) and definitive hosts (wild or domestic carnivore). The definitive hosts harbour the adult worm and are responsible of the eggs dispersion in the environment playing an

important role for parasite transmission. Humans can acquire infection by accidental ingestion of the *E. granulosus* s.l. eggs acting as aberrant host and representing an epidemiological dead end.

The actual taxonomical classification identifies *E. granulosus* s.l. as a group of five species (Romig et al., 2015): *E. granulosus sensu stricto* (s.s.; G1 and G3 genotypes), *E. equinus* (G4 genotype), *E. ortleppi* (G5 genotype), *E. canadensis* (G6-G8, G10 genotypes) and *E. felidis* (Hüttner et al., 2008). *E. granulosus* s.s. is responsible for the large part of the global burden of human CE (Alvarez Rojas et al., 2014). It has cosmopolitan distribution, especially present in pastoral and rural community, where it is principally maintained by a dog-sheep cycle (Eckert and Deplazes,

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<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.actatropica.2024.107151>

Received 10 October 2023; Received in revised form 27 January 2024; Accepted 15 February 2024

Available online 16 February 2024

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2004). *E. granulosus* s.s. is highly prevalent in South America, Australia, Asia and the Mediterranean Basin (Deplazes et al., 2017). A recent systematic review identified *E. granulosus* s.s. as the main responsible of human CE in the Mediterranean and Balkan countries during the last 20 years (Casulli et al., 2022). In Italy different epidemiological scenarios has been reported depending on the geographical area and associated socio-economic main activities (Loi et al., 2019; Piseddu et al., 2017). Specifically, in northern Italy, characterized by an intensive livestock production, the occurrence of *E. granulosus* s.s. is considered sporadic (prevalence < 1 %). On the contrary, in the southern regions, where 90 % of the entire Italian sheep population (7.3 million heads) is extensively raised, high prevalence of CE in humans and livestock has been recorded (Bonelli et al., 2020; Busi et al., 2007; Casulli et al., 2012; Garippa, 2006; Rinaldi et al., 2008). A retrospective study on ovine CE used a Bayesian approach to estimate the farm prevalence in Italy evidencing that the largest values are found in southern and insular regions (Sardinia, 19 %; Basilicata 12 %) (Loi et al., 2019). In these areas a similar situation applies for the human disease. In particular, the island of Sardinia is considered hyperendemic for human CE and recorded an annual incidence rate of hospital cases four times higher than the national average ($6.9/10^5$ versus $1.6/10^5$ inhabitants) (Brundu et al., 2014). As a matter of fact, the likelihood for humans of acquiring the infection in these areas is greater than in other parts of the country, considering the above-mentioned higher prevalence rates in livestock and the level of environmental contamination by *E. granulosus* eggs (Serra et al., 2022). This implies a corresponding annual economic burden of CE that was reported to be more pronounced in southern and insular Italy ($13,300 \text{ €}/10^5$ inhabitants) in comparison to central ($4900 \text{ €}/10^5$ inhabitants) and northern regions ($3300 \text{ €}/10^5$ inhabitants) (Piseddu et al., 2017).

Apart from *E. granulosus* s.s., a very small number of infection cases caused by *E. equinus* in horses (Varcasia et al., 2008), *E. ortleppi* in bovines (Casulli et al., 2008) and *E. canadensis* in domestic pigs and wild boar (Genchi et al., 2021; Laurimäe et al., 2019a; Varcasia et al., 2006) have been described in Italy. Previous studies have already reported the high genetic variability of *E. granulosus* s.l. (Addy et al., 2017; Boufana et al., 2014; Ohiole et al., 2019), and in particular of *E. granulosus* s.s., either regarding the more common G1 genotype and the less prevalent G3 genotype (Kinkar et al., 2018b, 2018c; Mehmood et al., 2022). If in some respect genetic variation may represent a selective advantage enabling the parasites survival, on the other hand, mutational events may determine phenotypical changes (i.e. antigenic profile, anthelmintic resistance properties) that can negatively affect the efficacy of diagnostic, prophylactic and therapeutic approaches against parasitic diseases (Gilleard and Beech, 2007; Ouellette, 2001). Furthermore, analysis of the genetic diversity of *E. granulosus* s.l. can contribute to the knowledge in the CE epidemiology, including transmission dynamics and host specificity, thus allowing to better counterpose an effective control strategy against the disease. To this purpose, the present study analysed CE cysts collected from infected sheep from various areas of mainland Italy and the island of Sardinia, with the main objective to investigate intergenotypic and intragenotypic variations of *E. granulosus* s.l. at national level.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Samples collection

CE cysts ($n = 126$) were collected from slaughtered sheep following post mortem inspection at local abattoirs. Sampling area covered several

Fig. 1. Map of the sampling area in Italy. Red dots indicate the sheep farms involved in the study.

Italian regions from northern (Lombardia, Veneto, Trentino-Alto Adige, Emilia Romagna), central (Lazio, Umbria, Abruzzo), southern (Campania, Basilicata) and insular (Sardegna) Italy (Fig. 1). Infected organs were sent to the National Reference Laboratory for Echinococcosis of Istituto Zooprofilattico Sperimentale della Sardegna (Sassari, Italy) for confirmatory diagnosis by DNA sequencing as described in the following paragraph. Parasite material was collected from CE cysts and stored at -80°C .

DNA extraction, PCR amplification and sequencing of *nad5* and *cox1* partial mitochondrial genes

Total genomic DNA was extracted from protoscolecocytes or germinal layers using the QIAGEN DNeasy Blood & Tissue as recommended by the manufacturer. (QIAGEN, Hilden, Germany). Amplification of the mitochondrial gene fragments, *nad5* (Kinkar et al., 2018a) and *cox1* (Nakao et al., 2000), was carried out as previously described. Sequencing was performed on both strands on a ABI-PRISM 3500 Genetic Analyzer (Applied Biosystems, Foster City, California, USA) with dRhodamine Terminator Cycle Sequencing kit (Applied Biosystems). Chromatogram analysis was performed using FinchTV software (freely available at <https://digitalworldbiology.com/FinchTV>). The consensus sequences of both mitochondrial regions were edited in BioEdit v7.0.0 (Hall, 1999).

2.2. Phylogenetic analyses

Molecular typing based on *cox1* sequences was performed by BLAST analysis against the NCBI database to identify species within *E. granulosus s.l.* complex. Bayesian evolutionary analysis based on *nad5* nucleotide sequences was performed in the software BEAST v1.10.4 (Suchard et al., 2018). The dataset for the Bayesian tree ($n = 260$) was composed of *E. granulosus s.s.* samples newly obtained in this study ($n = 126$) and included all the *nad5* haplotype available in GenBank, as detailed in supplementary Table 3 ($n = 134$); the alignment is available at Mendeley Data (Bonelli, 2024). BEAUti was used to import data, design the analysis and generate the xml file for BEAST. The Hasegawa-Kishino-Yano substitution model with a gamma distributed among-site rate variation (HKY+G) was calculated as the best fit evolutionary model using MEGA X (Kumar et al., 2018). The posterior distribution of parameters was assessed by Markov Chain Monte Carlo (MCMC). The length of chains was set at 50,000,000 states, logged every 1000 states with 10 % burn-in. The analysis of the output of BEAST and the convergence of MCMC run were assessed by the program Tracer v1.7.2 (Rambaut et al., 2018). The Bayesian tree, summarizing the posterior tree distribution, was created in TreeAnnotator v1.10.4 and visualised in FigTree v1.4.4.

Two DNA sequences datasets of *nad5* and *cox1* obtained in this study ($n = 126$) from samples of Italian origin were built for haplotype analysis (see Supplementary Tables). A third dataset ($n = 135$) composed of *nad5* and *cox1* concatenated sequences was built with sequences from this study ($n = 126$) and others of Italian origin retrieved from GenBank ($n = 9$; MG672136, MG672278- MG672281, MG682517, MG682518, MG682521, MG682522). Haplotypes of the Italian *nad5*, *cox1* and *nad5+cox1* datasets were identified with DNAsp v.6.12.01 (Rozas et al., 2017) and median-joining haplotype networks were calculated using PopART software (Bandelt et al., 1994). For *nad5* and *cox1* datasets, the population diversity indices and the neutrality tests were estimated in DnaSP and Arlequin v.3.5.2.2, respectively (Excoffier and Lischer, 2010).

3. Results

The nucleotide sequences of *nad5* and *cox1* mitochondrial partial regions were obtained from 126 CE cysts analysed. DNA sequences were aligned, trimmed to a length of 670 bp for *nad5* and 691 bp for *cox1* and deposited in GenBank (Supplementary Table 3). BLAST analysis based on *cox1* evidenced that *E. granulosus s.s.* was the only *Echinococcus* species infecting sheep in Italy. The Bayesian phylogenetic analysis

based on *nad5* (Fig. 2) identified among *E. granulosus s.s.* samples two well-resolved clades represented by G1 (posterior probability value = 0.95) and G3 genotype (posterior probability value = 1). The predominant genotype was G1 genotype ($n = 96$), matching the 76% of the samples collected in this study, while the remaining 24 % of the samples belonged to the G3 genotype ($n = 30$). Monophyletic groups, including a small number of isolates (2 to 5 samples) of different geographical origin, and characterized by high posterior probability values (>0.90) could be also evidenced within both G1 and G3 genotype.

The haplotype networks built on *nad5* (Fig. 3), *cox1* (Fig. 1 Supplementary material) partial gene revealed the presence of 40 and 33 haplotypes, respectively. As shown in (Table 1 Supplementary material), describing in detail the *nad5* haplotypes, out of the 40 haplotypes 29 belonged to G1 genotype and the remaining 11 haplotypes to the G3 genotype. Among the G1 genotype haplotypes, one predominant haplotype grouped 27 samples from different Italian regions, while 20 haplotypes were represented by a single sample. Three other haplotypes, separated by one mutational step from the main G1 haplotype, included 15 samples from Sardinia, central and southern Italy, 8 samples from northern Italy and 14 from Sardinia. The majority of G3 genotype samples grouped into two larger haplotypes including 12 samples and 8 samples from different Italian regions, respectively. One G3 haplotype composed of samples and 8 singleton haplotypes separated by one or two mutational steps were also evidenced. Fourteen singleton *nad5* haplotypes of Sardinian origin (G1=11; G3=3) were identified for the first time in this study.

Analysis of *cox1* haplotypes evidenced the presence of 33 haplotypes, many of them ($n = 19$) including G1 genotype isolates whereas 11 haplotypes grouped samples belonging to G3 genotype. Three haplotypes grouping mixed genotype (G1 and G3) samples were also found (Table 2 Supplementary material). Among the haplotypes associated to G1 genotype one predominant haplotype including 52 isolates and 20 distinct haplotypes represented just by one sample were present. It was also showed that out of 11 G3 haplotypes 9 were represented by one sample, one by two samples and another one by 5 samples. The three G1 and G3 mixed haplotypes included 4, 11 and 13 samples. Haplotype network based on *nad5+cox1* evidenced no mixed haplotypes and, similarly to *nad5* alone, allowed a good discrimination between genotypes (Fig. 2 Supplementary material). As shown in Table 1, the haplotype diversity for *nad5* was higher ($Hd = 0.914$) compared to that calculated for *cox1* ($Hd = 0.810$). Higher values of nucleotide diversity were also found for *nad5* ($\pi = 0.00512$) respect to *cox1* ($\pi = 0.00270$). The neutrality indices were significantly negative for both targets suggesting population expansion.

4. Discussion

Highly zoonotic species belonging to *E. granulosus s.l.* are maintained by a transmission cycle involving dogs, as definitive hosts, and sheep as intermediate hosts. Although considered marginal, sheep farming, representing 1.3 % of the total Italian agricultural output is to be considered a fundamental asset for livestock economy, especially in southern and insular Italy (“Tendenze e Dinamiche Recenti, Lattiero Caserai” 2023). In these areas, where sheep are extensively reared and favorable conditions for the perpetuation of the parasite cycle (i.e., large number of dogs, uncontrolled slaughtering, easy access to infected offal or carcasses by dogs) can be found, high CE prevalence rates among humans and animals have been reported (Deplazes et al., 2017; Loi et al., 2019; Otero-Abad and Torgerson, 2013). This study focused on ovine CE with the main objective to assess the genetic variability of *E. granulosus* infecting sheep in Italy. To this purpose, we analysed CE cysts samples collected from slaughtered sheep in northern, central, southern and insular Italy. We performed amplification of *cox1*, for initial screening of *E. granulosus s.l.* species, and *nad5* for *E. granulosus s.s.* genotyping. As expected, our results evidenced that *E. granulosus s.s.*, formerly known as “sheep strain”, is the only *Echinococcus* species infecting sheep in Italy.

Fig. 2. Bayesian phylogenetic tree built on partial nad5 DNA sequences of 260 *Echinococcus granulosus sensu stricto* samples. Posterior probability values with a colour gradient from light grey (value=0) to intense black (value=1) are reported on the branches. Sequences obtained in this study are shown in blue. The list of the sequences used are displayed in supplementary Table 3.

Fig. 3. Haplotype network calculated on partial nad5 DNA sequences of *Echinococcus granulosus sensu stricto* samples ($n = 126$) from Italy obtained in this study. Geographical distribution of the haplotypes is indicated by different colours as shown in the legend. Size of circles is proportional to the frequency of each haplotype. Number of mutations distinguishing the haplotypes is shown by hatch marks.

These findings are in agreement with previous studies performed both in insular Italy (Sardegna and Sicilia) (Bonelli et al., 2020; Giannetto et al., 2004; Mehmood et al., 2021) and in the Italian peninsula (Casulli et al., 2012). Several authors have also described the predominance of *E. granulosus* s.s. in Italy causing CE in other ruminants, particularly cattle and buffaloes (Capuano et al., 2006; Casulli et al., 2008), and in

humans (Casulli et al., 2022; Santucci et al., 2020). Recently, *E. granulosus* s.s. was also detected in two wolves in northern Italy, on the Italian side of the Western Alps (Orusa et al., 2022), and one wolf in central Italy, on the Umbria-Marche Apennines (Crotti et al., 2023).

In the past years, *E. granulosus* s.s genetic diversity was mainly investigated using cox1 and nad1 mitochondrial genes. These markers

Table 1

Diversity and neutrality indices for *E. granulosus* s.s. isolates based on nad5 and cox1 partial mitochondrial genes. Hn, number of haplotypes. Hd, haplotypes diversity. π , nucleotide diversity.

		<i>E. granulosus</i> s.s. genotypes				Diversity		Neutrality	
		n	G1	G3	Hn	Hd \pm s.d.	$\pi \pm$ s.d.	Tajima's D	Fu's Fs
nad5	Total	126	96	30	40	0.914 \pm 0.014	0,00,512 \pm 0,00,034	-1.55203*	-26.10268**
	Northern Italy	16	12	4	5	0,717 \pm 0,095	0,00,475 \pm 0,00,109	0,63,784	1.60714
	Central Italy	17	12	5	9	0,912 \pm 0,042	0,00,531 \pm 0,00,081	0,00,983	-1.70877
	Southern Italy	5	4	1	4	0,900 \pm 0,161	0,00,567 \pm 0,00,201	-0,85,540	0.05125
	Insular Italy (Sardinia)	88	68	20	32	0.903 \pm 0.018	0,00,507 \pm 0,00,043	-1,49,795*	-20.94378**
cox1	Total	126			33	0,810 \pm 0,033	0,00,270 \pm 0,00,021	-1.78625*	-27.57818**
	Northern Italy	16			7	0,750 \pm 0,092	0,00,294 \pm 0,00,040	-0.50358	-1.52218
	Central Italy	17			8	0,858 \pm 0,063	0,00,260 \pm 0,00,047	-1.23533	-3.25186*
	Southern Italy	5			4	0,900 \pm 0,161	0,00,318 \pm 0,00,068	-0.56199	-0.84824
	Insular Italy (Sardinia)	88			24	0,780 \pm 0,042	0,00,253 \pm 0,00,027	-1.64307*	-19.39085**

* p value<0.05; ** p value<0.001.

have represented an important tool for the molecular characterization of *E. granulosus* (Bowles et al., 1992; Bowles and McManus, 1993), but they have also shown to provide insufficient informative positions to discriminate G1 from G3 with confidence. On the other hand, the detection of polymorphisms on a short fragment of nad5 proposed by Kinkar et al., revealed to be a reliable diagnostic method for the identification of *E. granulosus* s.s. mitochondrial genotypes (Kinkar et al., 2018a). Accordingly, our results pointed out that, differently from cox1, nad5, alone or in combination with cox1, allowed distinctively the identification of G1 and G3 genotypes. In this study we evidenced a prevailing presence of G1 compared to G3 genotype with a ratio of about 3:1. G1 is considered the most prevalent genotype worldwide, as reported by previous studies using short mitochondrial DNA sequences (Alvarez Rojas et al., 2014; Casulli et al., 2012; Romig et al., 2015; Yanagida et al., 2012) and confirmed by more recent analyses on large portion of mitochondrial genome (Kinkar et al., 2018c, 2017; Laurimäe et al., 2016). These latter studies by Kinkar et al. allowed the identification of 4 haplotypes of G3 genotypes isolated from sheep in Italy (Kinkar et al., 2018c). As above mentioned, just in a small number of recently published scientific papers the distinction between *E. granulosus* s.s. G1 and G3 genotypes from animals and humans was performed on nad5 partial region (Bonelli et al., 2021; Crotti et al., 2023; Issa et al., 2022; Laurimäe et al., 2019b; Mehmood et al., 2021; Ohiolei et al., 2019; Samari et al., 2022; Santucci et al., 2023; Šoba et al., 2020). For this reason, it is difficult to compare our findings with other studies performed in Italy that have identified *E. granulosus* s.s genotypes with different and less discriminative genetic markers. Molecular characterization based on nad5 on animal samples collected in Italy was reported in just two studies performed on wild boars (*E. granulosus* s.s., n = 4; G1=2, G3=2) (Laurimäe et al., 2019a) and wild carnivores (*E. granulosus* s.s., n = 1; G3 in a Apennine wolf) (Crotti et al., 2023). Comparable proportions of G1 and G3, were evidenced in recent studies performed in dromedary camels (G1=67 %; G3=33 %) from Algeria (Samari et al., 2022) and in sheep (G1=96 %; G3=4 %) and yak (G1=87 %; G3=13 %) from Tibet (Ohiolei et al., 2019). Conversely, G3 genotype was found to prevail in cattle in Pakistan (Mehmood et al., 2022) with an inversed ratio (G1=21 %; G3=79 %) compared to other areas of the world. This predominance of G3 genotype infecting livestock in South Asia had been previously reported by morphological and molecular studies in India (Pednekar et al., 2009) and Pakistan (Latif et al., 2010). Furthermore, phylogeographic analyses of near-complete mitogenome sequences performed on Indian samples confirmed the higher prevalence of G3 genotype in this area and hypothesised an important role of India in the dispersion of G3 probably connected with the high presence of buffaloes (Kinkar et al., 2018c). In other countries, where buffalo farming is traditionally practiced, relative higher G3 prevalences were also observed, without being predominant over G1 (Capuano et al., 2006; Sharbatkhori et al., 2011).

The Bayesian phylogenetic tree built on a large dataset including all

the nad5 haplotypes available on GenBank, evidenced the presence of two well supported G1 and G3 clades along with other monophyletic clusters including samples from different geographical origin. This was also confirmed by BLAST analysis showing that sequences belonging to the largest G1 haplotype described in this study have 100 % similarity with isolates coming from several countries in Europe, Asia, America, Africa and Oceania. At the same time, G3 sequences belonging to the largest G3 haplotype showed 100 % similarity with isolates from Eastern Asia (China) Southern Asia (Pakistan, India) Middle East (Iran, Turkey) and Europe (Italy, France, Spain, Albania, Romania, Bulgaria). As already evidenced by other authors, both G1 and G3 sequences from different geographic regions are closely related. Phylogeographic studies have suggested a presumptive common origin for both *E. granulosus* s.s. genotypes in the Middle East and the consequent diffusion in other countries mainly shaped by the routes of animal trades (Casulli et al., 2012; Kinkar et al., 2018c, 2018b; Yanagida et al., 2012). On a smaller scale, the lack of geographical segregation was also evidenced by our results obtained on Italian samples.

The two founder nad5 haplotypes, belonging to G1 and G3 genotype, appeared not be associated with any Italian region, thus reflecting the animal movement between Sardinia and the peninsula and within the peninsula. The presence of smaller haplotypes including only sequences from a specific area, pictured the emergence of several local variants and the population expansion. This was also supported by diversity and neutrality analyses calculated on both nad5 and cox1. The high haplotype and low nucleotide diversity coupled with significant negative values of Tajima's D and Fu's Fs indicated high genetic variation and demographic expansion of *E. granulosus* s.s. in Italy, as already described by other authors in various parts of the world (Bonelli et al., 2020; Casulli et al., 2012; Kinkar et al., 2018b, 2018c; Yanagida et al., 2012).

In conclusion, the present study gave an estimation of *E. granulosus* s.s. G1 and G3 genotypes proportions in Italy. G1 genotype revealed to be the main cause of infection in sheep in Italy with a much higher percentage compared to G3. It was also evidenced that *E. granulosus* s.s. in Italy is characterized by high genetic variation with low genetic differentiation between Italian regions and between Italy and other distant countries. Broadening of the research focus on other intermediate hosts and enhancement of phylogenetic resolution by sequencing of larger portion of mitochondrial DNA are needed for a better understanding of *E. granulosus* s.s. genetic diversity in Italy.

Funding

This work was funded by RC IZS SA 01/19 from the Italian Ministry of Health.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Piero Bonelli: Conceptualization, Data curation, Formal analysis,

Visualization, Writing – original draft, Writing – review & editing. **Elisa Serra**: Data curation, Investigation, Writing – original draft. **Silvia Dei Giudici**: Data curation, Formal analysis, Visualization, Writing – review & editing. **Angela Peruzzu**: Investigation. **Silvia Crotti**: Investigation, Resources. **Patrizia Danesi**: Investigation. **Andrea Carvelli**: Investigation. **Toni Pisneddu**: Conceptualization, Funding acquisition, Project administration, Resources. **Giovanna Masala**: Funding acquisition, Project administration, Resources.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Data availability

I have submitted the dataset at Mendeley data (in moderation).

Acknowledgements

The authors would like to thank Dr. Marialuisa Buonanno (IZS del Mezzogiorno, Napoli, Italy), Monica Pierangela Cerioli (IZS della Lombardia ed Emilia-Romagna, Brescia, Italy), Manuela Iurescia (IZS del Lazio e Toscana, Roma, Italy), Annalisa Santi (IZS della Lombardia ed Emilia-Romagna, Bologna, Italy) for their precious collaboration.

Supplementary materials

Supplementary material associated with this article can be found, in the online version, at [doi:10.1016/j.actatropica.2024.107151](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.actatropica.2024.107151).

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